

Seguenzioidean gastropods from the continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula)

Gasterópodos seguenzioideos de la plataforma continental y talud de Galicia (NO Península Ibérica)

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ABSTRACT

More than 350 shells and specimens of seguenzioidean gastropods were found in samples from eight campaigns exploring the outer continental shelf and slope off Galicia (NW Spain) in the depth range 171-5314 m. They belong to 17 genera and 30 species. The most frequent species in the samples were *Anekes paucistriata*, *A. sculpturata*, *Putzesia wiseri* and *Danilia tinei*. Four of the species are identified with doubts, and three more only to the genus level. Taxonomic problems involving these doubtful species are commented. One species in Eudaroniidae is described as new: *Eudaronia diazagasi* n. sp.

RESUMEN

Se encontraron más de 350 conchas y especímenes de gasterópodos seguenzioideos en muestras de ocho campañas desarrolladas por la plataforma continental exterior y el talud frente a Galicia (NO de España) en el rango de profundidad 171-5314 m. Pertenecen a 17 géneros y 30 especies. Las especies más frecuentes en las muestras fueron *Anekes paucistriata*, *A. sculpturata*, *Putzesia wiseri* y *Danilia tinei*. Cuatro de las especies se identifican con dudas, y tres más solo a nivel de género. Se comentan los problemas taxonómicos que involucran a estas especies dudosas. Una especie de Eudaroniidae se describe como nueva: *Eudaronia diazagasi* n. sp.

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KEY WORDS: Mollusca, northeast Atlantic, taxonomy, Seguenziidae, Calliotropidae, Chilodontidae, Eudaroniidae, Pendromidae.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Atlántico noreste, taxonomía, Seguenziidae, Calliotropidae, Chilodontidae, Eudaroniidae, Pendromidae.

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INTRODUCTION

The present paper reviews the gastropods from the superfamily Seguenzioidea encountered in the samples gathered during eight cruises carried out along the continental shelf and slope off the coast of Galicia (NW Spain) between 2002 and 2009 by the Marine Biology Station of A Graña (belonging to Santiago de Compostela University). Results concerning rissoidean and conoidean gastropods from these same cruises have been recently published (OLIVER *ET AL.*, 2022a, 2022b).

The superfamily Seguenzioidea includes an enigmatic group of marine snails of worldwide distribution, mostly living in bathyal depths. Members of this superfamily are morphologically very diverse and include a combination of plesiomorphic and advanced characters, reason why some authors proposed for the group an intermediate range between Vetigastropoda and Caenogastropoda (SALVINI-PLAWEN & HASZPURNAR, 1987; HASZPURNAR, 1988). However, this group of gastropods has been recognized by some authors as a specialized off-shoot within or near the larger Trochoidea (e.g. BANDEL, 1979; QUINN 1983; HASZPRUNAR, 1993; HICKMAN, 1998; KANO, 2008), who considered that its apomorphic conditions independently derived from those in Caenogastropoda as a consequence of the small size and in response to deep-sea habitats. The concept of Seguenzioidea was extended by KANO (2008) and KANO *ET AL.* (2009) to include several “skeneimorph” taxa and those previously included in Eucyclinae and Cataeginae within Trochidae. Given the inclusion of these taxa, there are no clear morphological synapomorphies for this grouping, which is, however, well characterized in molecular phylogenies (PONDER, LINDBERG & PONDER, 2019). On the other hand, BANDEL (2010) proposed a different classification for some of the taxa now included in Seguenzioidea.

According to the phylogenomic analyses of CUNHA & GIRIBET (2021) Seguenzioidea is recovered as the sister group to all vetigastropods excepting pleurotomariids. Interestingly, it is the same position

as that of Seguenziidae in early morphological studies (PONDER & LINDBERG, 1997; SASAKI, 1998) and nowadays they are included in its own order Seguenziida within the subclass Vetigastropoda. According to recent literature, this order comprises eight families: Seguenziidae, Cataegidae, Chilodontidae, Choristellidae, Calliotropidae, Eudaroniidae, Pendromidae, Trochaclididae and Turcididae plus some genera without assigned family (MOLLUSCABASE, 2023).

Historical records on NE Atlantic seguenzioideans are included by WATSON (1886) and JEFFREYS (1878-1885), and more recently have been the subject of some publications (e.g. WARÉN, 1992; HOFFMAN, VAN HEUGTEN & LAVALEYE, 2010, 2011; HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2017, 2018; HOFFMAN, GOFAS & FREIWALD, 2020a,b).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material studied was obtained in different expeditions along the continental shelf and slope off the coast of Galicia (NW Spain). A map of the study area is provided in Figure 1 with locations of the sampling stations where the species studied have been obtained. Images of the representative habitats of the bottom samples are provided in Figure 2. Sampling methodology and processing of samples were described by PARAPAR & MOREIRA (2009) and in the previous works (OLIVER *ET AL.*, 2022a, 2022b). A list of the stations cited in this paper, with coordinates, depth, type of habitat and the acronyms of all projects, is given in the Appendix 1.

Benthic samples were taken in the depth range 171-5314 m by means of the following gears: Naturalist Dredge (DRN), Agassiz trawl (AT), Rock dredge (DRR) and Epibenthic sledge (EBS). Samples obtained were sieved and specimens were fixed with ethanol 70% neutralized with borax. Animals retained in sieves of ≥ 2 mm were sorted to high taxonomic levels on the Marine Biological Station of A Graña (University of Santiago de Compostela).

Figure 1. Sampling stations along Galician Continental Margin (NW Iberian Peninsula) where the studied shells and specimens have been found (figure made with GeoMapApp <www.geomapp.org> - CC BY).

Figura 1. Estaciones de muestreo a lo largo del Margen Continental de Galicia (NO Península Ibérica) donde se han encontrado las conchas y ejemplares estudiados (figura realizada con GeoMapApp <www.geomapp.org> - CC BY).

The entire collection of more than 350 shells and specimens from the samples studied have been deposited

(preserved dry and in 70% ethanol respectively) at the Museo de Historia Natural of the Universidade de Santiago

de Compostela, Galicia (Spain), with the deposit number: MHN-USC-10129.

Abbreviations used:

juv: juvenile

sh: empty shell

spc: shell with soft parts

MHN-USC: Museo de Historia Natural, University of Santiago de Compostela.

Expeditions:

CANGREXO I (1991)

DAI/02: DIVA-Artabria I (2002)

DAI/03: DIVA-Artabria I (2003)

VE/04: Vertidos (2004)

SAR/06-07: Sarridal (2007)

DAII/08: DIVA-Artabria II (2008)

SE/08: A Selva (2008)

FO/09: Forsagal (2009)

DAII/09: DIVA-Artabria II (2009)

RESULTS

The superfamily Seguenzioidea was represented in the studied samples (in the bathymetric range of 171-5314 m) by more than 350 shells and specimens belonging to 30 species (Table I), assigned to six families (Seguenziidae, Calliotropidae, Chilodontidae, Eudaroniidae, Pendromidae, and Trochaclidiidae) and 17 genera (seven of them without a family assigned). The most

frequent species in the samples were *Anekes paucistriata*, *A. sculpturata*, *Putzeysia wiseri* and *Danilia tinei*. Four of the species in the genera *Seguenzia*, *Calliotropis* and *Moelleriopsis* are identified with doubts, and three more species were tentatively assigned to the genus level, in the genera *Ancistrobasis* and *Anekes*. One species belonging to the genus *Eudaronia* are described as new.

Family SEGUENZIIDAE Verrill, 1884

Genus *Ancistrobasis* Dall, 1889

Type species: *Ancistrobasis*, *Basilissa costulata* Watson, 1879

Ancistrobasis reticulata (Philippi, 1844) (Fig. 3)

Solarium reticulatum Philippi, 1844: 149; pl. 25, fig. 6.

Type locality: Plio-Pleistocene, Valle del Río Lamato, Calabria, Italia.

Material examined: 18 shells (5 of them with soft parts) from 3 samples in the depth range 752-1191 m. Spain • 1 spc; 43°27'54"N, 09°29'11"W; 752 m; 28 Nov. 1991; CANGREXO-M13 • 2 sh; 43°57.030'N, 08°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 08°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 9 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 4 spc + 9 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 spc; 43°34.19'N, 09°22.12'W to 43°35.77'N, 09°21.23'W; 1005-1070 m; 19 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-04.

(Right page) Figure 2. Habitats representative of the diversity of the bottoms sampled. A: phosphorites from DA-I (03): DRN-600; B: live and dead coral gravel from DA-I (03): AT-1000; C: sand and small phosphorites from SE (08): DRN-11; D: phosphorites and carbonate crusts from SE (08): DRN-30-1; E: large stones, phosphorites, sand and coral from SE (08): AT-12; F: muddy sand from SE (08): EBS-14; G: small phosphorites and shells from DA-II (08): DRNp-2; H: small phosphorites DA-II (08): DRNp-03; I: sand with live and dead corals from SE (08): DRN-7; J: calcareous plates and muddy sand from DA-II (08): DRNp-22; K: mud from DA-II (09): EBS-1; L: living corals and stones from DA-II (09): DRR-47.

Figura 2. Hábitats representativos de la diversidad de los fondos muestreados. A: fosforitas de DA-I (03): DRN-600; B: grava de coral vivo y muerto de DA-I (03): AT-1000; C: arena y pequeñas fosforitas de SE (08): DRN-11; D: fosforitas y costras carbonatadas de SE (08): DRN-30-1; E: piedras grandes, fosforitas, arena y coral del SE (08): AT-12; F: arena fangosa del SE (08): EBS-14; G: pequeñas fosforitas y conchas de DA-II (08): DRNp-2; H: fosforitas pequeñas DA-II (08): DRNp-03; I: arena con corales vivos y muertos del SE (08): DRN-7; J: placas calcáreas y arenas fangosas de DA-II (08): DRNp-22; K: lodo de DA-II (09): EBS-1; L: corales vivos y piedras de DA-II (09): DRR-47.

Table I. Species studied. BG: recorded from the Galicia Bank (GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2020), AZ: South Azorean Seamount Chain (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2020a,b); CA: off Canary Islands (ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019; RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2013); ME: Mediterranean (WARÉN, 1992). An asterisk * indicates those species that are reported for the first time in Spanish waters.

Tabla I. Especies estudiadas. BG: citado del Banco de Galicia (GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2020), AZ: Cadena de montañas submarinas del sur de las Azores (HOFFMAN *ET AL.* 2020a,b); CA: frente a las Islas Canarias (ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019; RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2013); ME: Mediterráneo (WARÉN, 1992). Un asterisco * indica aquellas especies que se citan por primera vez en aguas españolas.

	BG	AZ	CA	ME
<i>Ancistrobasis reticulata</i> (Philippi, 1844)	X	X	X	
<i>Ancistrobasis</i> sp.				
* <i>Seguenzia</i> cf. <i>triteja</i> Salvador, Cavallari & Simone, 2014				
* <i>Calliotropis</i> cf. <i>ottoi</i> (Philippi, 1844)				X
<i>Calliotropis magadorensis</i> (Locard, 1898)				
* <i>Calliotropis</i> cf. <i>infundibulum</i> (Watson, 1879)				
<i>Toroidia toroides</i> (Hoffman, van Heugten & Lavaleye, 2011)			X	
<i>Danilia tinei</i> (Calcara, 1839)			X	X
<i>Putzeysia wiseri</i> (Calcara, 1839)				X
<i>Rugulina fragilis</i> (G.O. Sars, 1878)	X	X	X	X
* <i>Trochacis islandica</i> Warén, 1989		X		
<i>Trochacis versilensis</i> Warén, Carrozza & Rocchini, 1992	X	X		X
<i>Eudaronia aperta</i> (Sykes, 1925)		X		
* <i>Eudaronia diazagrasi</i> Templado & Oliver, n. sp.				
<i>Adeuomphalus ammoniformis</i> Seguenza, 1876		X		X
* <i>Adeuomphalus densicostatus</i> (Jeffreys, 1884)		X		X
* <i>Akritogyra curvilineata</i> Warén, 1992				
* <i>Akritogyra helicella</i> Warén, 1993				
<i>Anekes paucistriata</i> Warén, 1992	X	X	X	X
* <i>Anekes sculpturata</i> Warén, 1992				
<i>Anekes spiralis</i> Gofas & Luque, 2021	X			
<i>Anekes</i> sp. 1				
<i>Anekes</i> sp. 2				
* <i>Granigyra granulifera</i> Warén, 1992		X		X
<i>Lissotesta gittenbergeri</i> (van Aartsen & Bogi, 1988)			X	X
<i>Lissotesta turrita</i> (Gaglioni, 1987)				X
<i>Moelleriopsis messanensis</i> (Seguenza, 1876)				X
* <i>Moelleriopsis</i> cf. <i>richardi</i> (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896)		X		
<i>Vetulonia pauciviricosa</i> (Dautzenberg, 1889)	X			
<i>Trenchia biangulata</i> Rubio & Rolán, 2013	X	X	X	

Remarks: It is a common species in bathyal bottoms of NE Atlantic (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2011a, 2020a; HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2017; ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019). The western Atlantic *A. costulata* (Watson, 1879) has been considered a synonym of *A. reticulata*, although SALVADOR, CAVALLARI & SIMONE (2014) keep it as a valid species. The shells studied showed some variability in

their sculpture (see Fig. 3A, B) but the axial ribs were always prosocline. A live-collected specimen is shown in Figure 3A.

BANDEL (2010) figured a shell (as *A. reticulata*) from off-shore Cape Kennedy, Florida and about 400 m depth, but in that specimen the axial ribs are flexuous and the sculpture is made up of fewer spiral cords and axial ribs than in *A. reticulata* and *A. sp.*

Figure 3. *Ancistrobasis reticulata* (Philippi, 1844). A: shell with soft parts (CANGREXO I- M13); B: shell (SE/08 DRN-7) (4.4 × 5.5 mm); C: protoconch and first teleoconch whorl; D, E: details of sculpture, white frames on B and C respectively.

Figura 3. Ancistrobasis reticulata (Philippi, 1844). A: concha con partes blandas (CANGREXO I- M13); B: concha (SE/08 DRN-7) (4,4 × 5,5 mm); C: protoconcha y primera vuelta de teleoconcha; D, E: detalles de escultura, marcos blancos en B y C respectivamente.

Ancistrobasis sp. (Fig. 4)

Material examined: Only 1 shell with soft parts at 2121-2516 m. Spain • 1 spc; 44°14.929'N, 08°30.255'W to 44°15.367'N, 08°30.438'W; 2121-2516 m; 18 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-12.

Description: Shell broader than high (high 3.9 mm, width 5.0 mm in the shell studied), with 5 somewhat convex whorls, rather stout, moderately thick (Fig. 4A). Suture weakly marked. Sculpture of reticulate pattern of thin flexuous axial riblets and spiral cords, narrower than their interspaces with slightly pronounced nodules at intersections (Fig. 4D, E, G). Last whorl enlarged with rhomboid aperture. Base slightly convex, sculptured with dense spiral and radial cords (Fig. 4F). Umbilicus wide and deep (Fig. 4C). Lip flexuous, sharp, protruding above periphery. Smooth protoconch paucispiral with less than 1 whorl (Fig. 4B).

Remarks: The species differs from *A. reticulata* by its more convex whorls and base, less marked nodules, finer reticulated sculpture, wider umbilicus, and

rhomboid aperture. Its axial sculpture and lip is flexuous (procline in *A. reticulata*). HOFFMAN & FREIWALD (2017) described *Ancistrobasis lavaleyeyi* which shows an angular outline of the whorls due to prominent spiral cords. ORTEGA & GOFAS (2019) considered this last species as synonym of *A. reticulata* and they did not find any grounds for distinguishing more than one species of recent *Ancistrobasis* in the North Atlantic.

BANDEL (2010) figured a shell (as *A. reticulata*) from off-shore Cape Kennedy, Florida and about 400 m depth, but the axial ribs are flexuous and the sculpture is made up of fewer spiral cords and axial ribs than in *A. reticulata* and *A. sp.* BANDEL (2010) erected the family Ancistrobasidae for the genus *Ancistrobasis*.

Genus *Seguenzia* Jeffreys, 1876

Type species: *Seguenzia formosa* Jeffreys, 1876

Seguenzia cf. triteia Salvador, Cavallari & Simone, 2014 (Fig. 5)

Seguenzia triteia Salvador, Cavallari & Simone, 2014: 548, figs. 25-28.

Type locality: off São Mateus, Espírito Santo, continental slope of Abrolhos, Brazil, 19°01'S, 37°47'W, 1500-1575 m.

Material examined: Two juvenile shells with soft parts at 1373-5314 m. Spain • 1 spc (juv); 42°45.9'N, 09°41.68'W to 42°47.00'N, 09°42.12'W; 1499-1373 m; 29 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-27 • 1 spc (juv); 43°12.65'N, 13°23.38'W to 43°12.03'N, 13°23.28'W; 5305-5314 m; 112 Oct. 2009; DIVA ARTABRIA II/ EBS-01.

Remarks: This species found off Galicia most resembles *S. triteia*, previously known only from some shells found off Espírito Santo state South-eastern Brazil (SALVADOR ET AL., 2014). Thus, if the identification of this species is confirmed, *S. triteia* is reported here for the first time after its original description, greatly expanding its area of distribution to the north-eastern Atlantic. One of the two shells found is a young specimens of 2.3 mm high (Fig. 5A), whose characteristics coincide with those described for the

holotype of the species. Its entire surface is covered by very irregular microgranules (Fig. 5C, D), more densely packed in the teleoconch than in the protoconch. Unfortunately, the microsculpture cannot be appreciated in the holotype because the shell is dirty. The bulbous protoconch has a sculpture with chaotic microscopic ridges (Fig. 5B). It differs from *Seguenzia elegans* Jeffreys, 1885 in having a more elevated spire, and from *Seguenzia formosa* Jeffreys, 1876 in having a conspicuous sculpture.

Figure 4. *Ancistrobasis* sp. (SE/08 AT-12). A: shell (3.9 × 4.9 mm); B: protoconch and first teleoconch whorl; C: umbilical area; D-G: details of sculpture.

Figura 4. Ancistrobasis sp. (SE/08 AT-12). A: concha (3,9 × 4,9 mm); B: protoconcha y primera vuelta de teleoconcha; C: zona umbilical; D-G: detalles de la escultura.

Figure 5. *Seguenzia cf. triteia* Salvador, Cavallari & Simone, 2014: A: shell (2.3 × 2.0 mm) (DAII/08 EBS-27); B: protoconch; C, D: details of the sculpture and microsculpture of the teleoconch and protoconch respectively.

Figura 5. *Seguenzia cf. triteia* Salvador, Cavallari & Simone, 2014: A: concha (2,3 × 2,0 mm) (DAII/08 EBS-27); B: protoconcha; C, D: detalles de la escultura y microescultura de la teleoconcha y protoconcha respectivamente.

Family CALLIOTROPIDAE

Genus *Calliotropis* L. Seguenza, 1903

Type species: *Trochus otto* Philippi, 1844 by original designation

PÉREZ, FERRARI & EZCURRA (2022) consider the extant species of *Calliotropis* belonging to the family Calliotropidae, and that the Mesozoic and Paleogene

fossil representatives previously assigned to this genus should be placed in the family Eucyclidae, as it was initially proposed by HICKMAN (1988).

Calliotropis cf. otto (Philippi, 1844) (Fig. 6)

Trochus otto Philippi, 1844: 227, pl. 28 fig. 9.

Basilissa otto (Philippi, 1844) – MARTENS & THIELE, 1904: 126, pl. IV fig. 18.

Figure 6. *Calliotropis cf. ottoii* (Philippi, 1844). Shell with soft parts (17 × 15 mm) (DAII/08 DRNp-22). Figure 7. *C. mogadorensis* (Locard, 1898) (DAII/08 DRNp-04). Shell (9.5 × 9.0 mm).
Figura 6. *Calotropis cf. ottoii* (Philippi, 1844). *Concha con partes blandas* (17 × 15 mm) (DAII/08 DRNp-22).
Figure 7. *C. mogadorensis* (Locard, 1898) (DAII/08 DRNp-04). *Concha* (9,5 × 9,0 mm).

Lischkeia ottoii (Philippi, 1844) – ABBOTT, 1974: 39, fig. 265.

Calliotropis cf. ottoii Philippi – WARÉN, 1991: 56, fig. 1B.

Type locality: Plio-Pleistocene, Sicily.

Material examined: One shell with soft parts at 1727-1763 m. Spain • 1 spc; 43°05.28'N, 09°41.77'W to 43°06.25'N, 09°40.99'W; 1727-1763 m; 27 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-22.

After a detailed review of the bibliography related to this species, we conclude that the living specimens described by JEFFREYS (1884) and later authors are not conspecific with the one described by PHILIPPI (1844) from the Pleistocene, even more so when the type material seems lost. Until this matter is resolved, we prefer to name our specimen (Fig. 6) as *Calliotropis cf. ottoii*.

Recent specimens identified as *Calliotropis ottoii* are considered to have an amphiatlantic distribution, from Nova Scotia to off Carolina (ROSENBERG, 2009),

in the northwestern Atlantic, and from Iceland and Faroe Islands to the Mediterranean, in northeastern side, in the depth range 900-2500 m (COLMAN & TYLER, 1988; VILVENS & SWINNEN, 2008). ROMANI, GIUSTI & BOGI (2016) found a shell also identified as *C. ottoii* at about 400 depth off northern of Corsica, western Mediterranean. The living specimens here studied come from a bottom of calcareous concretions in muddy sand at about 1750 m. This species is recorded for the first time in Spanish waters.

Figure 8. *Calliotropis* cf. *infundibulum* (Watson, 1879) (FO/09 EBS-7). Shell with soft parts (10.1 x 10.0 mm).

Figura 8. *Calliotropis* cf. *infundibulum* (Watson, 1879) (FO/09 EBS-7). Concha con partes blandas (10,1 x 10,0 mm).

Calliotropis mogadorensis (Locard, 1898) (Figs. 7, 9A-D)

Solariella mogadorensis Locard, 1898: 24-25, figs. 1-4.

Calliotropis mogadorensis (Locard, 1898) – VILVENS & SWINNEN, 2008: 25, figs. 21-24.

Type locality: Off western Morocco, 1900 m.

Material examined: One empty shell at 1005-1070 m. Spain • 1 sh; 43°34.19'N, 09°22.12'W to 43°35.77'N, 09°21.23'W; 1005-1070 m; 19 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-04.

VILVENS & SWINNEN (2008) considered the species described by LOCARD (1898) as valid. They figured two syntypes and provided descriptive data.

The species was previously solely known from the type locality in the depth range 900-2000 m. IBARROLA ET AL. (2012) gave data on the soft parts and radula of some specimen from the Hatton Bank at 926 m depth that they identified as *C. otto*, but their imaged shell also seem to match the descriptions of *C. mogadorensis*. They suggest this possibility, but they keep them as *C. otto* given that the species described by

LOCARD (1898) was only known from off western Morocco. The shell here studied (Figs. 7, 9F) is from an intermediate locality in a similar bathymetric range.

The spire is more depressed in *C. mogadorensis* than in our *C. cf. otto*, slightly coeloeconoidal outline instead of slightly cyrtococonoidal, and the upper spiral cord is almost obsolete in the last whorl. Another species found in the area, *C. vaillanti* (P. Fischer, 1882), shows a wider and deeper umbilicus.

Distribution: off Portugal and W Spain, Azores, Madeira, Cape Verde (VILVENS & SWINNEN, 2008).

Calliotropis cf. *infundibulum* (Watson, 1879) (Figs. 8, 9E-H)

Trochus (*Margarita*) *infundibulum* Watson, 1879: 707-708.

Solariella infundibulum (Watson, 1879) – DALL, 1889: 380; CERNOHORSKY, 1977: 105, fig. 1.

Figure 9. *Calliotropis* spp. A-D. *C. mogadorensis* (Locard, 1898) (DAII/08 DRN-04p). A: protoconch; B-D: sculpture and microsculpture of the teleoconch. E-H. *C. cf. infundibulum* (Watson, 1879) (FORSA GAL/09 EBS-7). E: protoconch; F-H: sculpture and microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figura 9. Calliotropis spp. A-D. *C. mogadorensis* (Locard, 1898) (DAII/08 DRN-04p). A: protoconcha; B-D: escultura y microescultura del teleoconch. E-H. *C. cf. infundibulum* (Watson, 1879) (FORSA GAL/09 EBS-7). E: protoconcha; F-H: escultura y microescultura del teleoconch.

Calliotropis infundibulum (Watson, 1879) – POWELL, 1960: 130; MARSHALL, 1979: 531, figs. 4E-G, 9C-F.

Type locality: off Prince Edward Islands (Indian-Atlantic Ridge area), 46°46'S, 45°31'E, 2514 m.

Material examined: One shell with soft parts at 2390-2402 m. Spain • 1 spc; 42°11.48'N, 09°50.54'W to 42°13.09'N, 09°51.10'W; 2406-2402 m; 19 Feb. 2009; FORSAGAL EBS-7.

The shell studied (Figs. 8, 9A) differs from the two previous species of *Calliotropis* by its more globose outline, wider and open umbilicus and the stronger spiral cords forming the carinae that are in the middle of the whorls instead in the lower part. This shell conforms the published descriptions and figures of *C. infundibulum* (Watson, 1879), described from specimens from two very remote localities, off Bermuda (NW Atlantic) and off Marion – Prince Edward Islands (between South Africa and Antarctica). *Calliotropis infundibulum* has been recorded in deep water in very different geographic areas in the western Atlantic from off NE America to Brazil (CLARKE, 1962; ABBOT, 1974), in the eastern Atlantic off the Azores (LOCARD, 1898) and on the continental slope from off Morocco to off Senegal

(VILVENS, 2008), off South African sub-Antarctic islands (WATSON, 1879), Agulhas Bank off South Africa (MARTENS, 1903), south-western Pacific (MARSHALL, 1979), Japan (HIGO ET AL., 1999), normally deeper than 2000 m. A photograph was published by CERNOHORSKY (1977, fig. 1) as “the holotype” but there are seven specimens in total, which are therefore syntypes. VILVENS (2004, figs. 27-28, 2008, figs. 13-20) provided photos of some of those syntypes. Due to its disparate geographic distribution and variability, it possibly comprises a complex cryptic species. The specimen here studied was collected at 2400 m and it falls within the variability of the taxon, but differs from the type material by having fewer tubercles on the spiral cords. Therefore, we refer to it as *C. cf. infundibulum*.

Genus *Toroidia* Hoffman & Freiwald, 2018

Type species: *Toroidia merianae* Hoffman & Freiwald, 2018.

Toroidia toroides (Hoffman, van Heugten & Lavaleye, 2011) (Fig. 10)

Margarites toroides Hoffman, van Heugten & Lavaleye, 2011: 57-60, figs. 1-3.

Toroidia toroides (Hoffman, van Heugten & Lavaleye, 2011) – HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2018: 91.

Type locality: off NW Morocco (35.294° N-6.778° W) in 529 m.

Material examined: One empty shell at 581-566 m. Spain • 1 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C.

Remarks: The genus *Toroidia* includes three species differing in spire outline and sculptural details. HOFFMAN & FREIWALD (2018) illustrate several specimens of *Toroidia toroides* from different locations, which show certain degree of intraspecific variability. The shell here studied falls

within this variability. Its previous known distribution was restricted to a small area off NW Morocco and Canary Islands in the depth range 200-1050 m (HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2018; ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019). This record extends its area of distribution to the north.

Figure 10. *Toroidia toroides* (Hoffman, van Heugten & Lavaleye, 2011) (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: shell (2.1 × 1.5 mm); C, D: details of the sculpture of the teleoconch; E, F: protoconch and detail of its microsculpture.

Figura 10. Toroidia toroides (Hoffman, van Heugten & Lavaleye, 2011) (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: concha (2,1 × 1,5 mm); C, D: detalles de la escultura de la teleoconcha; E, F: protoconcha y detalle de su microescultura.

Family CHILODONTAIDAE

Genus *Danilia* Brusina, 1865

Type species: *Monodonta limbata* Philippi, 1844 (= *Monodonta tinei* Calcara 1839) by monotypy.

Danilia tinei (Calcara, 1839) (Fig. 11)

Monodonta tinei Calcara, 1839: 14, fig. 8.

Danilia tinei (Calcara, 1839) – MONTEROSATO, 1880: 252.

Danilia otaviana auct. non Cantraine, 1835.

Material examined: 18 shells with soft parts and 24 empty shells (many of them juveniles) from 10 samples in the depth range 312–720 m. Spain • 2 spc (juv) + 1 sh (juv); 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 598–610 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 6 spc (juv) + 1 sh (juv); 43°48.421'N, 08°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 08°51.091'W; 599–607 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-600 • 2 sh; polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00'W / 44°10'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00'W / 44°07'N, 08°35'W; 720 m; 5 Jan. 2007; SARRIDAL (06)-1 • 3 spc + 4 sh (2 juv); polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00'W / 44°10'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00'W / 44°07'N, 08°35'W; 417–668 m; 1 Aug. SARRIDAL (07)-3 • 1 spc (juv) + 2 sh (1 juv); polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00'W / 44°10'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00'W / 44°07'N, 08°35'W; 420–650 m; 12 Nov. 2007; SARRIDAL (07)-5 • 1 spc + 8 sh (5 juv); 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581–566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 spc + 1 sh; 44°07.495'N, 08°46.99'W to 44°07.675'N, 08°45.225'W; 416–407 m; 18 Jul. 2008; A SELVA AT-11-2 • 4 spc (juv); 43°48.511'N, 08°51.393'W to 43°49.92'N, 08°50.95'W; 312–576 m; 23 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-30-1 • 1 sh (juv); 44°06.94'N, 08°47.23'W to 44°07.17'N, 08°46.03'W; 440–429 m; 17 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-11-2 • 3 sh; 43°24.95'N, 09°25.5'W to 43°25.6'N, 09°24.62'W; 458–470 m; 20 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-07.

Danilia tinei is a moderately common eastern Atlantic species, ranging from Norway to Morocco and into the Mediterranean, also recorded from the Rockall Bank, Madeira, Cape Verde islands and on the Lusitanian seamounts, mainly in the deeper areas of the continental shelf and slope (TEMPLADO, 2011; HOFFMAN ET AL., 2011;

NEGRI & CORSELLI, 2026). It has not been found on the Galicia Bank (GOFAS ET AL. 2021). Some authors have found this species associated with white corals (i.e., HØISÆTER, T. 2009; MASTROTOTARO ET AL., 2010). The living specimens studied were found in samples from the continental slope with predominance of phosphorites.

Genus *Putzeysia* Sullioti, 1889

Type species: *Trochus clathratus* Aradas, 1847 by monotypy

Putzeysia wiseri (Calcara, 1842) (Fig. 12)

Trochus wiseri Calcara, 1842: 14.

Putzeysia wiseri (Calcara, 1842) – TRYON, 1889: 413, pl. 57, fig. 43.

Type locality: fossil material from outcrop in Sicily.

Material examined: 50 shells with soft parts and 12 empty shells from 12 samples in the depth range 312–1861 m. Spain • 2 spc; 43°47.188'N, 08°53.053'W to 43°55.312'N, 08°53.101'W; 770–842 m; 11 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-800 • 3 sh (2 juv); 43°57.030'N, 08°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 08°54.133'W; 1191–1132 m; 9 Sep. 2002; DIVA ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 11 spc (6 juv); 43°48.421'N, 08°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 08°51.091'W; 599–607 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-600 • 6 spc; 43°53.847'N, 08°57.324'W to 43°54.621'N, 08°57.261'W; 993–1004 m; 16 Sep. 2003; DIVA-

Figure 11. *Danilia tinei* (Calcara, 1839) (SAR/06-1). A, B: juvenile shell and detail of its sculpture (6.0 × 5.5 mm); C: aperture of an adult shell; D, E: apical view; F: protoconch.

Figura 11. *Danilia tinei* (Calcara, 1839) (SAR/06-1). A, B: concha juvenil y detalle de su escultura (6,0 × 5,5 mm); C: apertura de una concha adulta; D, E: vista apical; F: protoconcha.

ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 4 spc; 43°48.514'N, 08° 51.439'W to 43°49.163'N, 08°51.157'W; 616–616 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-600 • 16 spc + 5 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908–1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 spc + 3 sh (juv); 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581–566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 9 spc +sh; 43°48.511'N, 08°51.393'W to 43°49.092'N, 08°50.959'W; 312–576 m; 23 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-30-1 • 1 spc; 43°20.49'N, 09°34.03'W to 43°21.22'N, 09°32.96'W; 846–771 m; 25 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-16 • 1 sh; 42°55.76'N, 09°44.04'W to 42°55.79'N, 09°44.57'W; 709–728 m; 28 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-25 • 1 sh; 42°51.20'N, 09°43.85'W to 42°52.97'N, 09°44.25'W; 1861–1177 m; 28 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-26.

Putzeysia wiseri is a common species distributed from the NE Atlantic to the Mediterranean associated with carbonates or mixed substrata between 150 and 3000 m depth, more frequently between 200 and 2000 m (GUIDASTRI, MELONE & TAVIANI, 1984; GENIO, WARÉN, MATOS & CUNHA, 2013; NEGRI & CORSELLI, 2026), but it was not found in the Galicia Bank (GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2021). ENGL & ROLÁN (2009) described two new species of this genus in the Canary Islands, *Putzeysia franziskae*

and *P. jutae*, which had previously been cited as *P. wiseri* by ENGL (1994). Two additional species of *Putzeysia* have been described from Madeira, *P. cillisi* Segers, Swinnen & De Prins, 2009, and from the Mediterranean, *P. rickyi* Reitano & Scuderi, 2021. The fossil *Putzeysia clathrata* (Aradas, 1847), from the Early Pleistocene of Sicily and Calabria, previously considered as synonym of *P. wiseri*, has been proposed as a valid species by REITANO, SCUDERI & VILLARI (2022).

Figure 12. *Putzeysia wiseri* (Calcara, 1842) (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: shell and detail of its sculpture (4.8 × 4.2 mm). C: umbilical area. D-F: juvenile shell, protoconch and detail of its microsculpture. *Figura 12. Putzeysia wiseri* (Calcara, 1842) (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: concha y detalle de su escultura (4,8 × 4,2 mm). C: área umbilical. D-F: concha juvenil, protoconcha y detalle de su microescultura.

Family PENDROMIDAE

Genus *Rugulina* Palazzi, 1988

Type species: *Daronia monterosatoi* van Aartsen & Bogi, 1986, by original designation, Mediterranean Sea.

Rugulina fragilis (G.O. Sars, 1878) (Fig. 13)

Adeorbis fragilis G.O. Sars, 1878: 213, Tab. 22, fig. 19a-c.

Rugulina fragilis (G.O. Sars, 1878) – WARÉN, 1991: 72-73, figs 11A-E; 13A-B.

Type locality: off Norway, 100-346 m

Material examined: 23 shells (14 of them with soft parts) from 8 samples in the depth range 566-1106 m. Spain • 1 spc; 43°53.457'N, 08°48.461'W to 43°55.321'N, 08°53.101'W; 629-631 m; 11 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-600 • 3 spc; 43°57.030'N, 08°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 08°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 9 Sep. 2002; DIVA ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 7 spc + 6 sh (juv); 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 1 spc; 43°48.421'N, 08°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 08°51.091'W; 599-607 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-600 • 1 spc; 43° 48.514'N, 08° 51.439'W to 43° 49.163'N, 08°51.157'W; 616 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-600 • 1 sh (juv); 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08° 57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul.

Figure 13. *Rugulina fragilis* (G.O. Sars, 1878) (SE/08 DRN-7-C). A, B: living specimen (DAI/03 AT-600); C: shell (1.3 × 1.5 mm); D, E: apical whorls and protoconch; F: microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figura 13. *Rugulina fragilis* (G.O. Sars, 1878) (SE/08 DRN-7-C). A, B: ejemplar vivo (DAI/03 AT-600); C: concha (1,3 × 1,5 mm); D, E: vueltas apicales y protoconcha; F: microescultura de la teleoconcha.

2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 spc; 42°55.76'N, 09°44.04'W to 42°55.79'N, 09°44.57'W; 709-728 m; 28 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-25.

The taxon was reviewed by WARÉN (1992), who recorded it from eastern Greenland, Iceland and the Faroes, to Norway, in the depth range 60-970. Sub-

sequently *Rugulina fragilis* has been cited on the Seine Seamount, near Madeira (BECK *ET AL.*, 2006), Rockall Bank (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2010), Tyrrhenian and

Alboran seas in the Mediterranean (GIUSTI, SBRANA & ROMANI, 2015), Canary Islands (ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019), Atlantis and Plato seamounts south of the Azores (HOFFMAN ET AL., 2020b) and on the Galicia Bank (GOFAS ET AL., 2021). The specimens were found in samples in the depth range 566-

1100 m, where the rissoid *Alvania cimioides* dominated. The head and foot are yellowish and the visceral mass reddish (Fig. 13A, B). The cephalic tentacles are thick and verrucose and there are a number of yellow-dotted epipodial tentacles, long, thick and contractile.

Family TROCHACLIDAE

Genus *Trochaclis* Thiele, 1912

Type species: *Trochaclis antarctica* Thiele, 1912 by monotypy, Antarctic.

Trochaclis islandica Warén, 1989 (Fig. 14)

Trochaclis islandica Warén, 1989: 9-11, figs. 6-7.

Type locality: off Iceland.

Material examined: One fragmentary shell at 581-566 m. Spain • 1 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C.

Trochaclis islandica was originally recorded from Greenland, Iceland and Norway (WARÉN, 1989). It is also known from the Rockall-Hatton area (HOFFMAN ET AL. 2010) and the Plato seamount, south

of the Azores (HOFFMAN ET AL., 2020b). The regularly pitted sculpture of the protoconch (Fig. 14C, D) and the three cords in the umbilical area (Fig. 14B) confirm its identification as *T. islandica*.

Trochaclis versiliensis Warén, Carrozza & Rocchini, 1992 (Figs. 15, 16)

Trochaclis versiliensis Warén, Carrozza & Rocchini in Warén, 1992: 180, figs. 26E, 36A-D.

Type locality: Tuscan Archipelago, 300-400 m.

Material examined: 20 shells with soft parts from two samples in the depth range 428-600 m. Spain • 1 spc; polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00'W / 44°10'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00'W / 44°07'N, 08°35'W; 480-600 m; 19 Apr. 2007; SARRIDAL (07)-2 • 19 spc; 44°08.516'N, 08°40.788'W to 44°09.688'N, 08°39.721'W; 436-428 m; 17 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-11.

Trochaclis versiliensis is known from the Porcupine area and the Rockall Bank, Galicia Bank, the Lusitanian seamounts off NW Morocco and off Portugal, the south Azorean seamounts and the Mediterranean (WARÉN, 1992; HOFFMAN ET AL., 2018; HOFFMAN ET AL., 2020b). The taxon is characterized by two umbilical cords, one spiral cord on the initial teleoconch and by the regularly pitted protoconch. Most of the specimens studied (found in the same sample at 428-436 m from a muddy sand bottom with few phosphorites), so

this species seems to be gregarious. These specimens match the description and figures of the species (Fig. 15) The only shell found in another sample (SARRIDAL-2 at 480-600 m) presented some differences with respect to the rest of the specimens studied (Fig. 16). This shell is proportionally less tall and with a more closed umbilicus, like an umbilical fissure, and the umbilical cords are also reduced. However, both the protoconch and the keel at the beginning of the teleoconch coincide with those of the typical form.

Figure 14. *Trochaclis islandica* Warén, 1989 (SE/08 DRN-7C). A: shell (2.5 × 2.1 mm); B: umbilical cords; C, D: protoconch and detail of its microsculpture.

Figura 14. *Trochaclis islandica* Warén, 1989 (SE/08 DRN-7C). A: concha (2,5 × 2,1 mm); B: cordones umbilicales; C, D: protoconcha y detalle de su microescultura.

Family EUDARONIIDAE

Genus *Eudaronia* Cotton, 1945

Type species: *Cyclostrema* (*Daronia*) *jaffaensis* Verco, 1909 (by subsequent designation), SW Pacific, South Australia, off Cape Jaffa, 90 fathoms.

Eudaronia aperta (Sykes, 1925) (Fig. 17)

Homalogyra aperta Sykes, 1925: 192

Adeuomphalus laevis Rindone, 1990: 289

Eudaronia aperta (Sykes, 1925) – WARÉN, 1991: 80, figs. 14C-D, 18D.

Type locality: off Portugal (39°42'N-09°43'W; 1930 m)

Material examined: Only one empty shell at 908-1106 m. Spain • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

WARÉN (1991) recovered the genus *Eudaronia* to include the North Atlantic species *E. aperta*. Recently HOFFMAN *ET*

AL. (2020b) described two new species of this genus from the Azorean seamounts. Four shells of *Eudaronia* were found in

Figure 15. *Trochaclis versiliensis* Warén, Carrozza & Rocchini, 1992 (SE/08 EBS-11). A: shell with soft parts (2.0 × 1.7 mm); B, C: umbilicus and umbilical cord; D-F: protoconch and detail of its microsculpture.

Figura 15. *Trochaclis versiliensis* Warén, Carrozza & Rocchini, 1992 (SE/08 EBS-11). A: concha con partes blandas (2,0 × 1,7 mm); B, C: ombligo y cordón umbilical; D-F: protoconcha y detalle de su microescultura.

Figure 16. *Trochaclis cf. versiliensis* (SAR/07-2). A: shell with soft parts (1.8 × 1.5 mm); B, C: first whorls and protoconch; D: umbilical area.

Figura 16. Trochaclis cf. versiliensis (SAR/07-2). A: concha con partes blandas (1,8 × 1,5 mm); B, C: primeras vueltas y protoconcha; D: área umbilical.

the studied samples; we attribute one of them with doubts to *E. aperta* (Fig. 17) and the other (Fig.18) to a new species that is described below. *Eudaronia aperta* ranges from Iceland and Norway to Por-

tugal (WARÉN, 1991; HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2010; HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2017), and shells have been also found in the Plato Seamount (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2020b) in a sample taken at about 1500 m depth.

Eudaronia diazagrasi n. sp. Oliver & Templado (Fig. 18)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:FF4B3A67-CA7A-448A-A0A6-7DA32115E61D

Type material: 3 shells (2 of them with soft parts) from 2 samples in the depth range 417-668 m. *Holotype:* SPAIN • 1 sh; 43°48.421'N, 08°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 08°51.091'W; 599-607 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-600; Museo de Historia Natural, Santiago de Compostela, MHN-USC-10130. *Paratypes:* SPAIN • 2 spc; polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00' W / 44°10'N, 008°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00' W / 44°07'N, 08°35'W; 417-668 m; 15 Jul. 2007; SARRIDAL (07)-4; Museo de Historia Natural, Santiago de Compostela, MHN-USC-10131.

Type locality: Off NW Spain, Galicia, 43°48.421'N, 08°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 08°51.091'W; 599-607 m. ***Derivatio nominis:*** This species is dedicated to Dr. Guillermo Díaz-Agras, who has participated in the direction of all oceanographic campaigns and for the custody and management of the samples studied.

Figure 17. *Eudaronia aperta* (Sykes, 1925) (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: shell (diameter 0.98 mm); C, D: protoconch; E: microsculpture of the teleoconch; F: microsculpture of the protoconch.

Figura 17. *Eudaronia aperta* (Sykes, 1925) (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: concha (diámetro 0,98 mm); C, D: protoconcha; E: microescultura de la teleoconch; F: microescultura de la protoconcha.

Description: Minute, planorboid, inflated shell, symmetrical over peripheral plane with concave apical and abapical sides with weak keels (Fig. 18A, B). Diameter 1.2 mm. Colour white, translucent.

Protoconch: single planorboid whorl, small nucleus, exposed apically and abapically (Fig. 18C, D), sculpture chaotically

pitted surface (Fig. 18E), terminating with a slightly thickened, straight and smooth rim. Maximum width 165 μm. Transition to teleoconch clear by terminating rim and change in sculpture.

Teleoconch: 1½ whorls, flexuous fine growth lines with occasional coarse growth stages. Suture deeply impressed. Apical and abapical smooth spiral cords

Figure 18. *Eudaronia diazagrasi* Templado & Oliver, n. sp.. (DAI/03 DRN-600). A: apical view of the holotype (diameter 1.2 mm); B: abapical view; C: protoconch, apical view, width 165 µm; D: abapical view of protoconch; E: microsculpture of the protoconch; F: microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figura 18. Eudaronia diazagrasi Templado & Oliver, n. sp. (DAI/03 DRN-600). A-B: vista apical del holotipo (diámetro 1,2 mm); B: vista abapical; C: protoconcha, vista apical, ancho 165 µm; D: vista abapical de la protoconcha; E: microescultura de la protoconcha; F: microescultura de la teleoconcha.

with weak keels; apical cord slightly closer to periphery. Microsculpture of irregular axial rough grooves, weaker in peripheral area. Lip slightly flexuous, peripherally protruding, slightly

angular apically and abapically, terminating on penultimate whorl. Internally smooth, parietal callus thin.

Remarks: Placement in *Eudaronia* is based on the morphological similarity

Figure 19. *Adeuomphalus ammoniformis* Seguenza, 1876 (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: apical and abapical view of the shell. C, D: apical and abapical view of the protoconch.

Figura 19. *Adeuomphalus ammoniformis* Seguenza, 1876 (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: vista apical y abapical de la concha. C, D: vista apical y abapical de la protoconcha.

with the type species. The Atlantic *Eudaronia aperta* has a smooth initial teleoconch and an axially-aligned pitted micro-sculpture on the teleoconch (Fig. 18F) whereas our species has dense irregular axial micro-grooves. *Eudaronia mikra* Hoffman, Gofas & Frei-

wald, 2020 has a strong spiral cord with axial ribs on the initial teleoconch while our new species lacks these ribs. *Eudaronia spirata* Hoffman, Gofas & Freiwald, 2020 has spiral cordlets on the protoconch whereas our new species lacks these.

Family: not assigned

Genus *Adeuomphalus* Seguenza, 1876

Type species: *Adeuomphalus ammoniformis* Seguenza, 1876 by monotypy.

Adeuomphalus ammoniformis G. Seguenza, 1876 (Fig. 19)

Adeuomphalus ammoniformis Seguenza, 1876: 10.

Figure 20. *Adeuomphalus densicostatus* (Jeffreys, 1884) (DA-I/03 EBS-600). A: broken shell; B: protoconch and transition protoconch/teleoconch.

Figura 20. *Adeuomphalus densicostatus* (Jeffreys, 1884) (DA-I/03 EBS-600). A: concha rota; B: protoconcha y transición protoconcha/teleoconcha.

Type locality: Plio-Pleistocene, near Messina, Sicily.

Material examined: 4 empty shells from 2 samples in the depth range 420-1106 m. Spain • 1 sh; polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00'W / 44°00'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00'W / 44°07'N, 08°35'W; 420-650 m; 12 Nov. 2007; SARRIDAL (07)-5 • 3 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

Empty shells of *Adeuomphalus ammoniformis* have been recorded on several seamounts and banks of the northeastern Atlantic (BECK *ET AL.*, 2006; HOFFMAN &

FREIWALD, 2017; HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2010; 2020b) and dead or fossil in western Mediterranean (WARÉN, 1991). Not found on the Galicia Bank (GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2021).

Adeuomphalus densicostatus (Jeffreys, 1884) (Fig. 20)

Homalogyra densicostata Jeffreys, 1884: 129, pl. 10, fig 1.

Adeuomphalus densicostatus (Jeffreys, 1884) – KANO *ET AL.*, 2009: 403-404, figs. 1A-E.

Type locality: PALAZZI (1990) designated a lectotype from off Portugal (Porcupine Expedition 1870, stations 16 and 17a, 1000-2000 m depth).

Material examined: One shell with soft parts (broken during SEM procedures) at 598-610 m. Spain • 1 spc; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600.

As the preceding species, *Adeuomphalus densicostatus* is known from several banks and seamount of north-eastern Atlantic (HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2017; HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2010; 2020b) and

off southern Portugal (PALAZZI, 1990; KANO *ET AL.* 2009) in the depth range 305-2175 m, and dead or fossil in western Mediterranean (WARÉN, 1992; NEGRI & CORSELLI, 2016).

Genus *Akritogyra* Warén, 1992

Type species: *Akritogyra curvilineata* Warén, 1992 by original designation.

Figure 21. *Akritogyra curvilineata* Warén, 1992 (SAR/07-2). A: shell; B, C: protoconch and detail of its microsculpture; D: umbilicus.

Figura 21. *Akritogyra curvilineata* Warén, 1992 (SAR/07-2). A: concha; B, C: protoconcha y detalle de su microescultura; D: ombligo.

Akritogyra curvilineata Warén, 1992 (Fig. 21)

Akritogyra curvilineata Warén, 1992: 162-163, figs 14C-D, 15D-F.

Type locality: Bay of Biscay, bathyal.

Material examined: Only one empty shell at 480-600 m. Spain • 1 sh; polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00' W / 44°10'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N; 09°00'W / 44°07'N; 08°35'W; 480-600 m; 19 Apr. 2007; SARRIDAL (07)-2.

Akritogyra curvilineata has been recorded from Iceland to southwestern Portugal (WARÉN, 1992). The species can be identified by its flexuous growth

lines and lip (Fig. 21A, D). The protoconch has a rough nucleus and is smooth towards the slightly flared rim (Fig. 21B, C).

Akritogyra helicella Warén, 1993 (Fig. 22)

Akritogyra helicella Warén, 1993: 182, fig. 21.

Type locality: Southwestern Iceland, Reykjanes Ridge, 260-300 m.

Material examined: Only one empty shell at 908-1106 m. Spain • 1 sh; 44° 11.65'N, 08°58.15'W to 44°11.54'N, 08°57.57'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

Figure 22. *Akritogyra helicella* Warén, 1993 (SE/08) DRN-7). A, B: shell; C: apical view of its protoconch; D: growth lines of the teleoconch.

Figura 22. *Akritogyra helicella* Warén, 1993 (SE/08) DRN-7). A, B: concha; C: vista apical de su protoconcha; D: líneas de crecimiento de la teleoconcha.

This species was previously only known from its type material (the holotype and one paratype) dredged off southwestern Iceland. Despite the geo-

graphical remoteness, the shell found (Fig. 22A-D) perfectly matches the holotype of *A. helicella* described and figured by WARÉN (1993).

Genus *Anekes* Bouchet & Warén, 1979

Type species: *Anekes undulisculpta* Bouchet & Warén, 1979, by original designation.

Anekes paucistriata Warén, 1992 (Fig. 23)

Anekes paucistriata Warén, 1992: 165-166, figs. 19D, 20B-d, 21A, 22B.

Type locality: Gorringe Bank (36°33.7'N-11°30.1'W), 305-320 m.

Material examined: More than 100 specimens and shells (about half of them with soft parts) from 10 samples, in the depth range 480-1499. Spain • >50 spc + >50 sh; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 1 sh; 43°48.514'N, 08° 51.439'W to 43°49.163'N, 08°51.157'W; 616 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-600 • 1 sh; 43°35.611'N, 08°58.536'W to 43°36.104'N, 08°57.284'W; 384-345 m; 24 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-EBS-400 • 2 sh; 43°36.544'N, 09°03.064'W to 43°36.816'N, 09°04.339'W; 601-619 m; 28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-EBS-600 • 1 sh; polygon delimited by points 44°10'N, 09°00'W / 44°10'N, 08°35'W / 44°00'N, 09°00'W / 44°07'N, 08°35'W; 480-600 m; 12 Nov. 2007; SARRIDAL (07)-5 • 7 sh; 44°08.65'N,

08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 4 spc; 44°00.806'N, 08°33.098'W to 44°01.967'N, 08°32.57'W; 346-344 m; 17 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-14 • 2 spc; 43°48.252'N, 08°51.427'W to 43°49.707'N, 08°51.164'W; 575-584 m; 23 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-30-1 • 1 sh; 43°34.86'N, 09°21.95'W to 43°36.44'N, 09°20.71'W; 1010-1112 m; 19 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-04 • 2 spc; 42°45.9'N, 09° 41.68'W to 42°47.00'N, 09°42.12'W; 1499-1373 m; 29 Sep. 2008; DIV-ARTABRIA II EBS-27.

Anekes paucistriata is a common species known in northeastern Atlantic seamounts (WARÉN, 1992; BECK ET AL., 2006; HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2017; HOFFMAN ET AL., 2010, 2020b), including the Galicia Bank (GOFAS ET AL., 2021). It has been also recorded from the northwestern slope of Gran Canaria (Canary Islands) (ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019)

and in the Sicily Channel (WARÉN, 1992). This species has turned out to be very abundant in the sample DIVA-ARTABRIA (03) I EBS-600 at about 600 m depth.

Some variability has been observed in the shells studied, regarding the outline and in the development of the sculpture (see Fig. 23A, I, J).

Anekes sculpturata Warén, 1992 (Fig. 24)

Anekes sculpturata Warén, 1992: 167, figs. 17A, 19C, 20A, 22A, 28A.

Type locality: SE Bay of Biscay (44°36'N, 02°08'W, 230-330 m).

Material examined: 48 shells (6 of them with soft parts), from 9 samples in the depth range 171-619 m. Spain • 1 spc; 43°40.250'N, 08°43.755'W to 43°40.760'N, 08°42.120'W; 207-197 m; 12 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-200 • 18 sh; 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 3 sh; 43°35.611'N, 08°58.536'W to 43°36.104'N, 08°57.284'W; 384-345 m; 24 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-EBS-400 • 18 sh; 43°36.544'N, 09°03.064'W to 43°36.816'N, 09°04.339'W; 601-619 m; 28 Sep. 2004; VERTIDOS GA-EBS-600 • 1 spc + 1 sh; 44° 06.943'N, 08° 47.232'W to 44°07.173'N, 08°46.031'W; 440-429 m; 17 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-11-2 • 1 spc; 44°05.687'N, 08°24.558'W to 44°07.253'N, 08°24.302'W; 337-330 m; 17 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-13 • 1 spc + 1 sh; 44°00.806'N, 08°33.098'W to 44°01.967'N, 08°32.57'W; 346-344 m; 17 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-14 • 1 sh; 43°58.84'N, 08°15.625'W to 43°59.621'N, 08° 14.285'W; 233-237 m; 16 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-20 • 2 spc; 43°31.687'N, 08°52.188'W to 43°33.149'N, 08°53.142'W; 171-182 m; 23 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-23.

Anekes sculpturata was previously only known from the original description (WARÉN, 1992) in southeastern Bay of Biscay and off Banyuls, Mediterranean coast of France, in circalittoral

bottoms. This species has been relatively abundant in the deep shelf and slope of the area studied, but it has not been cited in the Galicia Bank (GOFAS ET AL., 2021).

Anekes spiralis Gofas & Luque, 2021 (Fig. 25)

Anekes spiralis Gofas & Luque, 2021: 48-51, fig. 17A-H.

(Right page) Figure 23. *Anekes paucistriata* Warén, 1992. A: shell (1.1 × 1.1 mm) with a test of the foraminifer *Orbulina* plugged in the aperture (SE/08 DRN-7); B: lateral view of its protoconch; C: umbilical area; D: detail of the microsculpture at the beginning of the teleoconch. E-G: apical view of another shell (0.9 mm) (SE/08 EBS-14), detail of the microsculpture at the beginning of its teleoconch, and protoconch; H: detail of the microsculpture (DAII/08 EBS-04); I: shell (0.9 × 0.8 mm) (DAI/03 EBS-600); J: oblique apical view; K: detail of the microsculpture of the teleoconch; L-N: protoconch.

Figura 23. *Anekes paucistriata* Warén, 1992. A: concha (1,1 × 1,1 mm) con un caparazón del foraminífero *Orbulina taponado* en la apertura (SE/08 DRN-7); B: vista lateral de su protoconcha; C: zona umbilical; D: detalle de la microescultura al inicio de la teleoconcha. E-G: vista apical de otra concha (0,9 mm) (SE/08 EBS-14), detalle de la microescultura al inicio de su teleoconcha, y protoconcha; H: detalle de la microescultura (DAII/08 EBS-04); I: concha (0,9 × 0,8 mm) (DAI/03 EBS-600); J: vista apical oblicua; K: detalle de la microescultura de la teleoconcha; L-N: protoconcha.

Figure 24. *Anekes sculpturata* Warén, 1992 (SE/08 EBS-14). A: shell (0.9 × 1 mm); B: detail of its microsculpture; C: apical view; D-F: protoconch and details of its microsculpture.

Figura 24. Anekes sculpturata Warén, 1992 (SE/08 EBS-14). A: concha (0,9 × 1 mm); B: detalle de su microescultura; C: vista apical; D-F: protoconcha y detalles de su microescultura.

Type locality: Galicia Bank (42°56.77' N, 11°58.53' W; 1631 m).

Material examined: Only one shell with soft parts (broken after SEM procedures) at 1373-1499 m. Spain • 1 spc; 42°45.9'N, 09°41.68'W to 42°47.00'N, 09°42.12'W; 1499-1373 m; 29 Sep. 2008; DIVA ARTABRIA II EBS-27.

Figure 25. *Anekes spiralis* Gofas & Luque, 2021 (DAII/08 EBS-27). A: shell (1.8 × 1.6 mm); B: microsculpture; C, D: protoconch; E: discontinuity at the beginning of the teleoconch; F: microsculpture of the umbilical area.

Figura 25. *Anekes spiralis* Gofas & Luque, 2021 (DAII/08 EBS-27). A: concha (1,8 × 1,6 mm); B: microescultura; C, D: protoconcha; E: discontinuidad al inicio de la teleoconcha; F: microescultura de la zona umbilical.

This is the first record of the species, with its peculiar microsculpture, after its

original description in the Galicia Bank (GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2021).

Anekes sp. 1 (Fig. 26)

Material examined: One empty shell at 1373-1499 m. Spain • 1 sh; 42°45.9'N, 09°41.68'W to 42°47.00'N, 09°42.12'W; 1373-1499 m; 29 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-27.

Figure 26. *Anekes* sp. 1 (DAII/08 EBS-27). A-B: shell (1.1 mm); C: umbilical area; D, E: protoconch; F: detail of the microsculpture.

Figura 26. *Anekes* sp. 1 (DAII/08 EBS-27). A-B: concha (1,1 mm); C: área umbilical; D, E: protoconcha; F: detalle de la microsculptura.

The outline of the shell studied (Fig. 26A, B) is similar to some species of *Anekes* and quite similar to *Akritogyra curvilineata* Warén, 1992, especially to the specimen from Iceland (WARÉN, 1992, fig. 13D) but differs from the holotype (coming from the Bay of Biscay) in details from its sculpture, typical of *Anekes*. In the shell studied the proto-

conch shows an irregular granulation (Fig. 26D, E) and the beginning of the teleoconch has a denser granulate microsculpture followed by scattered linear segments of mainly spiral orientation (Fig. 26E, F). The umbilical area has small granules (Fig. 26C), instead of pits, as in *A. curvilineata*. Therefore, we prefer not to assign it a specific identification.

Figure 27. *Anekes* sp. 2 (SE/08 DRN-7): A: juvenile shell; B, C: protoconch; D: Detail of the sculpture of the teleoconch; E: another juvenile shell; F: sculpture of umbilical area.

Figura 27. *Anekes* sp. 2 (SE/08 DRN-7): A: concha juvenil; B, C: protoconcha; D: Detalle de la escultura del teleoconch; E: otra concha juvenil; F: escultura de la zona umbilical.

Anekes sp. 2 (Fig. 27)

Material examined: Only 2 juvenile empty shells from one sample at 908-1106 m. Spain • 2 sh (juv); 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

The two juvenile shells found (Fig. 27A, E) fit major characteristics of *Anekes affinis*; their sculpture of cross-linked raised lines and the protoconch with rough sculp-

ture (WARÉN, 1992: fig. 18) (Fig. 27A, B, D, F). Spiral cords in the wide umbilical area are however untypical (Fig. 27F). Hence, we refer to the species as *Anekes* sp. 2.

Figure 28. *Granigyra granulifera* Warén, 1992 (DAII/08 EBS-27. A: shell (2.2 mm); B, C: protoconch; D, E: microsculpture.

Figura 28. *Granigyra granulifera* Warén, 1992 (DAII/08 EBS-27. A: concha (2,2 mm); B, C: protoconcha; D, E: microescultura.

Genus *Granigyra* Dall, 1889

Type taxon: *Granigyra limata* (Dall, 1889) by monotypy.

Granigyra granulifera Warén 1992 (Fig. 28)

Granigyra granulifera Warén, 1992: 176-177, figs. 32E-F, 34B, 35A-E.

Type locality: Bay of Biscay, 05°00'N, 06°00'E, 2460-2500 m (Biomedes 1976).

Material examined: 3 shells (one of them with soft parts), at 1373-1499 m. Spain • 1 spc + 2 sh; 42°45.9'N, 09°41.68'W to 42°47.00'N, 09°42.12'W; 1499-1373 m; 29 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-27.

Granigyra granulifera has been recorded in bathyal bottoms from the Bay of Biscay, off south Portugal,

Madeira, Little Meteor Seamount and western Mediterranean (WARÉN, 1992; HOFFMAN ET AL., 2020b).

Genus *Lissotesta* Iredale, 1915

Type species: *Cyclostrema micra* Tenison Woods, 1877 by original designation.

Lissotesta gittenbergeri (van Aartsen & Bogi, 1988) (Fig. 29)

Anekes gittenbergeri van Aartsen & Bogi, 1988: 28, figs. 1-2.

Lissotesta gittenbergeri (van Aartsen & Bogi, 1988) – WARÉN, 1992: 172, figs. 26A-29D-F.

Figure 29. *Lissotesta gittenbergeri* (van Aartsen & Bogi, 1988) (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: shell (0.8×0.7 mm) and its protoconch; C-E: another shell (0.7 mm), its protoconch and details of its microsculpture; F, G: another shell (0.7×0.5 mm) and detail of its apical whorls.

Figura 29. *Lissotesta gittenbergeri* (van Aartsen & Bogi, 1988) (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: concha ($0,8 \times 0,7$ mm) y su protoconcha; C-E: otra concha ($0,7$ mm), su protoconcha y detalles de su microescultura; F, G: otra concha ($0,7 \times 0,5$ mm) y detalle de sus vueltas apicales.

Type locality: Central Tyrrhenian Sea, dredged at 200 m depth.

Material examined: 14 empty shells in 6 samples in the depth range 417-1191 m. Spain • 1 sh; $43^{\circ}57.030'N$, $08^{\circ}54.795'W$ to $43^{\circ}57.248'N$, $08^{\circ}54.133'W$; 1191-1132 m; 9 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 1 sh; $43^{\circ}48.587'N$, $08^{\circ}51.402'W$ to $43^{\circ}49.545'N$, $08^{\circ}51.197'W$; 610-598 m; 18 Sep. 2003;

Figure 30. *Lissotesta turrita* (Gagliani, 1987) (DAI/02 AT-1000). A: shell with soft parts (0.8 × 0.7 mm); B, C: protoconch; D: operculum; E: umbilical area.

Figura 30. *Lissotesta turrita* (Gagliani, 1987) (DAI/02 AT-1000). A: concha con partes blandas (0,8 × 0,7 mm); B, C: protoconch; D: opérculo; E: área umbilical.

DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 3 sh; polygon delimited by points 44°10.00'N, 09°00.00'W / 44°10.000'N, 08°35.00'W / 44°00.00'N, 09° 00.00'W / 44°07.00'N, 08°35.00'W; 417-668 m; 15 Jul. 2007; SARRIDAL (07)-4 • 9 sh; 44°11.652' N, 08°58.152' W to 44°11.539' N, 08°57.574' W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 sh; 44°08.65'N, 08°55.305'W to 44°08.771'N, 08°55.104'W; 581-566 m; 20 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7C • 1 sh; 44°05.923'N, 08°45.586'W to 44°06.046'N, 08°43.886'W; 432-453 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA EBS-10-2B.

Lissotesta gittenbergeri is characterized by the globose outline of the shell (Fig. 29A) with thick equidistant spiral cords

(Fig. 29C, F, G) and uncoiled domed protoconch (Fig. 29B, D, G). The characteristic spiral cords almost disappear in the last

Figure 31. *Moelleriopsis messanensis* (Seguenza, 1876) (SE/08 DRN-11). A: shell (diameter 1.9 mm); B: lateral view of the upper part of the shell; C: umbilical area; D: protoconch.

Figura 31. *Moelleriopsis messanensis* (Seguenza, 1876) (SE/08 DRN-11). A: concha (diámetro 1,9 mm); B: vista lateral de la parte superior de la concha; C: área umbilical; D: protoconcha.

whorl of some of the specimens studied (Fig. 29A), but the rest of the characters agree with those of the species, especially regarding its characteristic protoconch.

This was previously recorded from the Tyrrhenian and Alboran seas,

western Mediterranean, and in nearby seamounts southwest Portugal (VAN AARTSEN & BOGI, 1988; WARÉN, 1992; RUBIO, 2011). The present finding extends its distribution area to the north.

Lissotesta turrata (Gaglini, 1987) (Fig. 30)

Cyclostrema turratum Monterosato, 1875: 23 (nom. nud.)

Cyclostrema turratum Gaglini, 1987: 5.

Anekes nofroni van Aartsen & Bogi, 1988: 29.

Anekes turrata (Gaglini, 1987) – BOGI & NOFRONI, 1989: 142.

Lissotesta turrata (Gaglini, 1987) – WARÉN, 1992: 172-173, figs. 26B, 30A-F.

Type locality: Palermo, Sicily, 90 m.

Material examined: Only one shell with soft parts, at 1132-1191 m. Spain • 1 spc; 43°57.030'N, 08°54.795'W to 43°57.248'N, 08°54.133'W; 1191-1132 m; 9 Sep. 2002; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000.

Lissotesta turrata was previously known from southwestern Iceland, western Norway, Galicia Bank, Ibero-Moroccan Gulf and Western Mediterranean (GAGLINI, 1987; WARÉN, 1992,

1996). In the Mediterranean and in the neighbouring Atlantic it has been found in deep circalittoral bottoms (90-300 m) and in bathyal bottoms in northeastern Atlantic.

Figure 32. *Moelleriopsis* cf. *richardi* (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896) (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: shell (1.2 mm in diameter); C, D: protoconch.

Figura 32. *Moelleriopsis* cf. *richardi* (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896) (SE/08 DRN-7). A, B: concha (1,2 mm de diámetro); C, D: protoconcha.

Genus *Moelleriopsis* Bush, 1897

Type species: *Moelleriopsis abyssicola* K.J. Bush, 1897, by original designation

Moelleriopsis messanensis (Seguenza, 1876) (Fig. 31)

Cyclostrema messanensis Seguenza, 1876: 188.

Moelleriopsis messanensis (Seguenza, 1876) – WARÉN, 1992: 174-175, figs. 26D-31B-D.

Type locality: Sicily, Upper Pliocene.

Material examined: Only one empty shell, at about 438-459 m. Spain • 1 sh; 44°09.896'N, 08°39.581'W to 44°10.129'N, 08°39.494'W; 438-459 m; 18 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-11.

Moelleriopsis messanensis was previously found from the Bay of Biscay, Lusitanian seamounts, Ibero-Moroccan Gulf and West-Central Mediterranean in the depth range 350-2500 m (WARÉN, 1992; ROMANI & BOGI, 2016).

These late authors proposed provisionally place *Moelleriopsis* in the family Skeneidae. For now, we keep this genus within “unassigned” Seguenzioidea until its systematic position is clarified.

Figure 33. *Vetulonia paucivaricosa* (Dautzenberg, 1889). A: shell (2.8 × 2.8 mm) (DAII/08 EBS-10); B, C: shell (2.9 mm) (DAII/08 DRNp-02) and apical view of its protoconch; D-G: juvenile shell (1.6 × 1.9 mm) (DAII/08 EBS-4), umbilical area, lateral view of it protoconch, detail of its microsculpture; H: microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figura 33. Vetulonia paucivaricosa (Dautzenberg, 1889). A: concha (2,8 × 2,8 mm) (DAII/08 EBS-10); B, C: concha (2,9 mm) (DAII/08 DRNp-02) y vista apical de su protoconcha; D-G: concha juvenil (1,6 × 1,9 mm) (DAII/08 EBS-4), área umbilical, vista lateral de su protoconcha, detalle de su microescultura; H: microescultura de la teleoconcha.

Moelleriopsis cf. *richardi* (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896) (Fig. 32)

Cyclostema richardi Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896: 484-485, pl. 21 figs. 7-9.

Moelleriopsis richardi (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896) – HOFFMAN, GOFAS & FREIWALD, 2020: 40-41, fig. 34.

Material examined: Only one empty shell at 908-1106 m. Spain • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

The shell showed in Figure 32 resembles *Moelleriopsis richardi* for its strong umbilical cords, but differs from this species by its depressed outline

without a raised spire. This species is known from off the Azores and South Azorean Seamount Chain (HOFFMAN ET AL., 2020b).

Genus *Vetulonia* Dall, 1913

Type species: *Vetulonia galapagana* Dall, 1913.

Vetulonia paucivaricosa (Dautzenberg, 1889) (Fig. 33)

Trochus cancellatus Jeffreys, 1883: 96, pl. 20 fig. 4.

Solariella cancellata var. *paucivaricosa* Dautzenberg, 1889: 64, pl. 4, figs. 11a-d

Vetulonia jeffreysi Dall, 1913: 87.

Vetulonia josephinae Dall, 1927: 120.

Vetulonia paucivaricosa (Dautzenberg, 1889) – HOFFMAN ET AL., 2011: 99, figs. 86-87.

Type locality: off the Azores.

Material examined: 9 shells (three of them with soft parts) in 8 samples between 598 and 1211 m depth. Spain • 1 sh (juv); 43°48.421'N, 08°51.453'W to 43°49.160'N, 08°51.091'W; 599-607 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I DRN-600 • 1 sh (juv); 43°48.587'N, 08°51.402'W to 43°49.545'N, 08°51.197'W; 610-598 m; 18 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I EBS-600 • 1 sh (juv); 43°53.847'N, 08°57.324'W to 43°54.621'N, 08°57.261'W; 993-1004 m; 16 Sep. 2003; DIVA-ARTABRIA I AT-1000 • 2 sh (1 juv); 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7 • 1 sh; 43°34.86'N, 09°21.95'W to 43°36.44'N, 09°20.71'W; 1010-1112 m; 19 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-04 • 1 spc; 43°32.89'N, 09°30.88'W to 43°33.79'N, 09°29.60'W; 1211-1207 m; 21 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II EBS-10 • 1 spc; 43°33.35'N, 09°08.31'W to 43°36.81'N, 09°07.34'W; 546-523 m; 16 Sep. 2008; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRNp-02 • 1 spc; 42°26.856'N, 11°19.96'W to 43°26.852'N, 11°19.93'W; 1202-1203 m; 29 Oct. 2009; DIVA-ARTABRIA II DRN-47.

Vetulonia paucivaricosa is widely distributed in northeastern Atlantic, known from the Rockall and Hatton Banks to the

Ibero-Moroccan Gulf, including the Galicia Bank (HOFFMAN ET AL., 2011a, GOFAS ET AL., 2021) in the depth range 550-1500 m.

Genus *Trenchia* Knudsen, 1964

Type species: *Trenchia wolffi* Knudsen, 1964.

Trenchia biangulata Rubio & Rolán, 2013 (Fig. 34)

Trenchia sp. Beck, Metzger & Freiwald, 2002

Trenchia biangulata Rubio & Rolán, 2013: 2-4, figs. 1-6.

Figure 34. *Trenchia biangulata* Rubio & Rolán, 2013 (SELVA/08-DRN7). A-C: shell (diameter 1.1 mm); D: protoconch; E: detail of the microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figura 34. Trenchia biangulata Rubio & Rolán, 2013 (SELVA/08-DRN7). A-C: concha (diámetro 1,1 mm); D: protoconcha; E: detalle de la microescultura de la teleoconcha.

Type locality: Galicia Bank, 800-1000 m

Material examined: Only one empty shell in a sample taken between 908 and 1106 m. Spain • 1 sh; 44°11.652'N, 08°58.152'W to 44°11.539'N, 08°57.574'W; 908-1106 m; 19 Jul. 2008; A SELVA DRN-7.

Trenchia biangulata is known off Canary and Selvagens islands, from a seamount located between Canary

Islands and Portugal and in the Galicia Bank (BECK *ET AL.*, 2002; RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2013) in the depth range 60-1000 m.

DISCUSSION

Seguenzioidea includes several hundred species with a wide range of body size and morphology (KANO, 2008). In the current state of knowledge, this superfamily comprises two groups of species

regarding their size and general appearance. On the one hand, the commonly called “skeneimorph seguenziids” comprise a group of genera of very small and fragile species, usually less than 5 mm in

height, belonging to the families Seguenziidae, Cataegidae, Choristellidae, Eudaroniidae, Pendromidae, Trochaclididae, Turcicidae, as well as all “skeneimorphs” that were not yet assigned to a family. On the other hand, larger and more robust species belonging to the families Chilodontidae and Calliotropidae has been included within this superfamily based on anatomical and molecular evidence (BOUCHET & ROCROI, 2017; KANO, 2008; KANO ET AL., 2009). In the material here studied we have found species from all these families except Cataegidae (without any species in the Atlantic and Mediterranean), Choristellidae and Turcicidae.

Seguenzoid gastropods are common inhabitants of the bathyal bottoms worldwide with a patchy distribution, although there are very few records of most of the species and these are rarely represented by large suites of shells. In fact, more than 50% of the species found in the studied area were represented by single specimens (17 species), only six were represented by more than 10 specimens. Fifteen of the species were only found as empty shells. This is an indication that the family is insufficiently sampled and that rare species make up a considerable proportion of the seguenzoid fauna, so finding live specimens is extremely serendipitous. Furthermore, the small size and fragility of most species means that many of them can get lost during sampling or subsequent processing. As a consequence of the few specimens available for many of the species, their distribution and variability are not known and they are left in open or tentative nomenclature. This is the case of several of the species studied belonging to the genera *Seguenzia*, *Calliotropis*, *Eudaronia*, *Rugulina*, *Akritogyra* and *Moelleriopsis*.

Of the about 60 extant species of seguenzoid gastropods known in the N Atlantic / Mediterranean area, just over half of them have been found in the study area. All the species considered here were collected deeper than 100 m, and nine of them were only found deeper than 1000 m (*Ancistrobasis* sp., *Seguenzia* cf. *triteia*, *Calliotropis* cf. *ottoi*,

Calliotropis mogadorensis, *Calliotropis* cf. *infundibulum*, *Anekes spiralis*, *Anekes* sp., *Granigyra granulifera* and *Lissotesta turrita*). Sample A-SELVA (08) DRN-7 (at 908-1106 m in a bottom of sand with dead a live corals) stands out, in which 12 of the studied species were found.

It is noteworthy that only eight of the species studied have been recorded from the Galicia Bank (GOFAS ET AL., 2020), a large seamount located close to the studied area about 120 miles off the northwest coast of Galicia. In any case, the absence of records in a group in which most of species are rare should not be interpreted as not present, but may be due to the inadequate sampling of the deep benthos. Apart from the disparity of the findings of these species, the absence of some of them in the Galicia Bank (*Toroidia toroides*, *Moelleriopsis messanensis*, *Danilia tinei*, *Putzeysia wiseri*, *Akritogyra helicella*, *Anekes sculpturata*, *Moelleriopsis messanensis*) may be due to that they preferentially inhabit depths of about 650 m, which is the depth of the summit of this bank. In contrast, the seguenzoid species *Calliotropis vaillanti* (P. Fischer, 1882), *Seguenzia elegans* Jeffreys, 1885, *Seguenzia formosa* Jeffreys, 1876, *Carenzia carinata* (Jeffreys, 1877), *Asthelys munda* (Watson, 1879), *Mikro minimus* (Seguenza, 1876), *Granigyra pruinosa* (Jeffreys, 1883), *Granigyra tenera* (Jeffreys, 1883), *Granigyra inflata* (Warén, 1992), and *Adeuomphalus sinuosus* (Sykes, 1925), recorded in the Galicia Bank (GOFAS ET AL., 2020), have not been found in the studied samples. In addition to the reasons stated above, the differences in species composition between the Galician Bank and the deep continental shelf and slope off Galicia may also be due to environmental differences, such as the type of sediment, among others, the pelagic ooze and bioclastic silty sand in the bank and mainly terrigenous sediments on the continental shelf and the availability of suitable food resources.

Eleven of the species here reported (Table I) are additions to the malacofauna of Spanish waters, in an update to the national check list of GOFAS ET AL. (2017). These are *Seguenzia* cf. *triteia*, *Calliotropis* cf. *ottoi*, *Calliotropis* cf. *infundibu-*

lum, *Trochaclis islandica*, *Eudaronia diazagrasi* n. sp., *Adeuomphalus densicostatus*, *Akritogyra helicella*, *A. curvilineata*, *Anekes mikrosulpta*, *Anekes sculpturata*, and *Granigyra granulifera*.

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Appendix 1. Coordinates, depth and habitat of the collecting stations of Seguenzioidean species (n° sp: Number of specimens and species involved; see below key to abbreviations of species names).

Abbreviations for species mentioned in Appendix 1

Aa: <i>Adeomphalus ammoniformis</i>	A2: <i>Anekes</i> sp. 2	Mm: <i>Moelleriopsis messanensis</i>
Ac: <i>Akritogyra curvilineata</i>	Ci: <i>Calliotropis</i> cf. <i>infundibulum</i>	Mr: <i>Moelleriopsis</i> cf. <i>richardi</i>
Ad: <i>Adeomphalus densicostatus</i>	Co: <i>Calliotropis</i> cf. <i>ottoi</i>	Pw: <i>Putzeysia wiseri</i>
Ah: <i>Akritogyra helicella</i>	Cm: <i>Calliotropis mogadorensis</i>	Rf: <i>Rugulina fragilis</i>
Ai: <i>Ancistrobasis</i> sp.	Dt: <i>Danilia tinei</i>	St: <i>Seguenzia</i> cf. <i>triteia</i>
Ak: <i>Anekes spiralis</i>	Ea: <i>Eudaronia aperta</i>	Tb: <i>Trenchia biangulata</i>
Ap: <i>Anekes paucistriata</i>	Eg: <i>Eudaronia diazagrasi</i> n. sp.	Ti: <i>Trochaclis islandica</i>
Ar: <i>Ancistrobasis reticulata</i>	Gg: <i>Granigyra granulifera</i>	Tt: <i>Torodia toroides</i>
As: <i>Anekes sculpturata</i>	Lg: <i>Lisstotesta gittenbergeri</i>	Tv: <i>Trochaclis versiliensis</i>
At: <i>Anekes</i> sp. 1	Lt: <i>Lisstotesta turrita</i>	Vp: <i>Vetulonia paucivaricosa</i>

Station	N° sp.	Coordinates	Depth (m)	Habitat
CANGREXO –I (1991)= Acronym: CANGREXO I (1991)– Dates: 04-07-1991 & 11-12 1991				
M-13	1: Ar	43° 27' 54" N; 009° 29' 11" W	752	Ferromanganese nodules, with calcareous plates, coal slag and small stones
DIVA-ARTABRIA I (2002). Acronym: DA-I (02) – Dates: 08-15/09/2002				
AT-600	1: Rf	43° 53,457' N; 008° 48,461' W 43° 54,000' N; 008° 48,524' W	629-631	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts
AT-800	1: Pw	43° 47,188' N; 008° 53,053' W 43° 55,312' N; 008° 53,101' W	770-842	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts
AT-1000	5: Ar-Lg-Lt-Pw-Rf	43° 57,030' N; 008° 54,795' W 43° 57,248' N; 008° 54,133' W	1191-1132	Phosphorites and coral gravel
DIVA-ARTABRIA I (2003). Acronym: DA-I (03) – Dates: 10-20/09/2003				
DRN-600	5: Dt-Ed-Pw-Rf-Vp	43° 48,421' N; 008° 51,453' W 43° 49,160' N; 008° 51,091' W	599-607	Phosphorites
AT-600	3: Ap-Pw-Rf	43° 48,514' N; 008° 51,439' W 43° 49,163' N; 008° 51,157' W	616-616	Phosphorites
AT-1000	2: Pw-Vp	43° 53,847' N; 008° 57,324' W 43° 54,621' N; 008° 57,261' W	993-1004	Live and dead coral gravel
EBS-200	1: As	43° 40,250' N; 008° 43,755' W 43° 40,760' N; 008° 42,120' W	207-197	Muddy sand
EBS-600	7: Ad-As-Dt-Lg-Rf-Vp	43° 48,587' N; 008° 51,402' W 43° 49,545' N; 008° 51,197' W	610-598	Sand
VERTIDOS (2004). Acronym: VE – Dates: 17-21/09/2004 and 24-28/09/2004				
GA-EBS-400	2: Ap-As	43° 35,611' N; 008° 58,536' W 43° 36,104' N; 008° 57,284' W	384-345	Muddy sand
GA-EBS-600	2: Ap-As	43° 36,544' N; 009° 03,064' W 43° 36,816' N; 009° 04,339' W	601-619	Muddy sand

Station	Nº sp.	Coordinates	Depth (m)	Habitat
SARRIDAL (2006-07). Acronym: SARRI – Dates: 05/01/06 – 19/04/07– 15/07/07– 01/08/07– 12/11/07				
SARRI-1	1: Dt	44° 10,0' N; 009° 00,0' W 44° 10,0' N; 008° 35,0' W 44° 00,0' N; 009° 00,0' W 44° 07,0' N; 008° 35,0' W	720	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts. All samples are from an area delimited by the 4 points in A Selva
SARRI-2	2: Ac-Tv	44° 10,0' N; 009° 00,0' W 44° 10,0' N; 008° 35,0' W 44° 00,0' N; 009° 00,0' W 44° 07,0' N; 008° 35,0' W	480-600	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts. All samples are from an area delimited by the 4 points in A Selva
SARRI-3	1: Dt	44° 10,0' N; 009° 00,0' W 44° 10,0' N; 008° 35,0' W 44° 00,0' N; 009° 00,0' W 44° 07,0' N; 008° 35,0' W	417-668	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts. All samples are from an area delimited by the 4 points in A Selva
SARRI-4	2: Ed-Lg	44° 10,0' N; 009° 00,0' W 44° 10,0' N; 008° 35,0' W 44° 00,0' N; 009° 00,0' W 44° 07,0' N; 008° 35,0' W	417-668	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts. All samples are from an area delimited by the 4 points in A Selva
SARRI-5	3: Aa-Ap-Dt	44° 10,0' N; 009° 00,0' W 44° 10,0' N; 008° 35,0' W 44° 00,0' N; 009° 00,0' W 44° 07,0' N; 008° 35,0' W	420-650	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts. All samples are from an area delimited by the 4 points in A Selva
A SELVA-2008. Acronym: SE – Dates: 15-24/07/2008				
DRN-7	12: Aa-Af-Ah-Ar-A2-Ea-Lg-Mr-Pw-Rf-Tb-Vp	44° 11,652' N; 008° 58,152' W 44° 11,539' N; 008° 57,574' W	908-1106	Sand with live and dead corals
DRN-7C	7: Ap-Dt-Lg-Pw-Rf-Ti-Tt	44° 08,65' N; 008° 55,305' W 44° 08,771' N; 008° 55,104' W	581-566	Sand and corals
DRN-11	1: Mm	44° 09,896' N; 008° 39,581' W 44° 10,129' N; 008° 39,494' W	438-459	Sand and small phosphorites
DRN-30-1	2: Dt-Pw	43° 48,511' N; 008° 51,393' W 43° 49,092' N; 008° 50,959' W	312-576	Phosphorites and carbonate crusts
AT-11-2	1: Dt	44° 07,495' N; 008° 46,999' W 44° 07,675' N; 008° 45,225' W	416-407	Phosphorites and stones
AT-12	1: Ai	44° 14,929' N; 008° 30,255' W 44° 15,367' N; 008° 30,438' W	2121-2516	Large stones, phosphorites, sand and coral
EBS-10-2B	1: Lg	44°05.923'N, 008°45.586'W 44°06.046'N, 008°43.886'W	432-453	Volanta: Art of Artisanal Fishing
EBS-11	1: Tv	44° 08,516' N; 008° 40,788' W 44° 09,688' N; 008° 39,721' W	436-428	Slightly muddy sand and few phosphorites
EBS-11-2	2: Dt-As	44° 06,943' N; 008° 47,232' W 44° 07,173' N; 008° 46,031' W	440-429	Muddy sand
EBS-13	1: As	44° 05,687' N; 008° 24,558' W 44° 07,253' N; 008° 24,302' W	337-330	Muddy sand
EBS-14	2: Ap-As	44° 00,806' N; 008° 33,098' W 44° 01,967' N; 008° 32,57' W	346-344	Muddy sand

Station	N° sp.	Coordinates	Depth (m)	Habitat
EBS-20	1: As	43° 58,84' N; 008° 15,625' W 43° 59,621' N; 008° 14,285' W	233-237	Muddy sand
EBS-23	1: As	43° 31,687' N; 008° 52,188' W 43° 33,149' N; 008° 53,142' W	171-182	Muddy sand
EBS-30-1	1: Ap	43° 48,252' N; 008° 51,427' W 43° 49,707' N; 008° 51,164' W	575-584	Phosphorites and muddy sand
DIVA-ARTABRIA II (2008). Acronym: DA-II (08) – Dates: 15-30/09/2008				
DRNp-02	1: Vp	43° 33,35' N; 009° 08,31' W 43° 36,81' N; 009° 07,34' W	546-623	Small phosphorites
DRNp-03	1: Pw	43° 24,64' N; 009° 31,56' W 43° 25,38' N; 009° 30,97' W	880-814	Small phosphorites
DRNp-04	2: Ar-Cm	43° 34,19' N; 009° 22,12' W 43° 35,77' N; 009° 21,23' W	1005-1070	Sand and small phosphorites
DRNp-07	1: Dt	43° 24,95' N; 009° 25,5' W 43° 25,6' N; 009° 24,62' W	458-470	Phosphorites, stones and shells
DRNp-16	1: Pw	43° 20,49' N; 009° 34,03' W 43° 21,22' N; 009° 32,96' W	846-770	Sand with phosphorites, calcareous plates and stones
DRNp-22	1: Co	43° 05,28' N; 009° 41,77' W 43° 06,25' N; 009° 40,99' W	1727-1763	Phosphorites
DRNp-26	1: Pw	42° 51,20' N; 009° 43,85' W 42° 52,97' N; 009° 44,25' W	1861–1177	Dead coral and shells
EBS-04	2: Ap-Vp	43° 34,86' N; 009° 21,95' W 43° 36,44' N; 009° 20,71' W	1010-1112	Coarse sand with gravel
EBS-10	1: Vp	43° 32,89' N; 009° 30,88' W 43° 33,79' N; 009° 29,60' W	1211-1207	Sand
EBS-25	2: Pw-Rf	42° 55,76' N; 009° 44,04' W 42° 55,79' N; 009° 44,57' W	709-728	Rocks
EBS-27	5: Ap-Ak-A1-Gg-St	42° 45,9' N; 009° 41,68' W 42° 47,00' N; 009° 42,12' W	1499-1373	Mud with gravel
FORSAGAL (2009). Acronym: FOR – Dates: 14-25/02/2009				
EBS-7	1: Ci	42° 11,480' N; 009° 50,54' W 42° 13,09' N; 009° 51,10' W	2406-2402	Sand
DIVA-ARTABRIA II (2009). Acronym: DA-II (09) – Dates: 08-15/09/2002				
DRR-47	1: Vp	42° 26,856' N; 011° 19,96' W 42° 26,852' N; 011° 19,93' W	1202-1203	Living corals and stones
EBS-1	1: St	43° 12,65' N; 013° 23,38' W 43° 12,03' N; 013° 23,28' W	5305-5314	Mud